

Policy Brief No. [1]

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CYRENE
Certifying the Security and Resilience of
Supply Chain Services (SCS)

Who is this for?

Policy makers working in **Supply Chain Services (SCS) security issues** including privacy, accountability, resilience, cybersecurity certification, conformity assessment and cyber risk assessment

Highlights

1

In the literature the definition of Supply Chain Services (SCS) is not clear.

2

The security of Supply Chain Services is most important for the trustworthiness of the European Digital Single Market (DSM).

3

Certifying the security of SCS is an important mitigation measure for bringing confidence to global digital markets

4

EUCC scheme (Common Criteria based European candidate cybersecurity certification scheme) proposed by ENISA was used by CYRENE to propose the EUSCS (Common Criteria based cybersecurity certification scheme for the Supply Chain Services)

5

A collaborative online Security Management System for the SCS (SCS-ISMS) can serve as an accelerator in the SCS risk and conformity assessment processes, necessary in the certification.

Supply Chain Service (SCS) Security

All critical sectors (e.g.: transport, energy, health, financial) base their business activities on Supply Chain Services (SCSs). Delivering goods (e.g. vehicles, pharmaceuticals, people) is a typical SCS in all sectors. During the pandemic for example, we widely realized how important the secure, global distribution and delivery of the vaccines was.

Common threats of the SCSs include: theft, environmental damage, masquerading of identities, terrorism, physical damage, strikes, eavesdropping, interception of emissions or sensitive information, assets hijacking, traffic and/or data manipulation, data poisoning, social engineering, malware, identity or data privileges abuse, delocalization signals spoofing or jamming, failures and malfunctions of the cyber SCS assets.

The exploitation of these threats can lead to a variety of impacts, such as cargo and goods stealing, sensitive and critical data theft, illegal trafficking, systems damage or destruction, environmental disaster, or even human injuries or death. Additional impacts for the organisations such as economic paralysis, financial loss and costs, kidnapping, fraud and money steal are also in this long list.

Ensuring the secure provision of the SCSs at national, European and even more importantly at international level is a great challenge. The European project [CYRENE](#) considers security certification of the SCSs as a main mitigation measure and it proposes a cybersecurity scheme, risk and conformity assessment methodologies and a tool to realize the SCS certification process.

Poly-perceptivity of a SCS

A Supply Chain Service is one that its provision requires the operation of an ecosystem (processes, partners, systems). There are many ways to describe a SCS. In **CYRENE** we have classified the following escalated definitions depending upon the view adopted:

Overall Business perspective:

The SCS overall business view relies on the identification, analysis and assessment of any business driven SCS element that has a direct input for the provision of the SCS. As such, in this view, details of processes, business partners (i.e. suppliers, stakeholders, importers, vendors, manufacturers, authorities, governmental bodies) and their third parties, facilities, related business logic (e.g.: data and information flows, decision making), and any legal/regulatory restrictions are considered.

Holistic Technical perspective:

The SCS holistic-technical view is an asset-based interdependent view of the SCS. It builds upon the overall business view, i.e. it embeds all business processes, business partners

as well as all cyber and physical assets hosted by the different business partners for the provision of the SCS processes. SCS asset models revealing asset-interdependencies accompany the presentation of the SCS under this view.

Sector-Specific Technical perspective:

The SCS sector-specific technical view is an individual view (snapshot) of the SCS, i.e. the view that an individual business partner adopts: It consists of that business partner's processes and assets in the SCS (it is a segment of the SCS).

Technical-Component perspective:

This deeper view builds upon the last two technical views by revealing also all the components of the cyber SCS-assets (e.g.: chips, operating systems, storage, input/output / communication devices, processors).

EU policies for SCS and CYRENE

The 2021 ENISA report on Supply Chain attacks ([ENISA 2021](#)) has listed various attacks e.g.: malware infection, social engineering, brute-force attacks, counterfeiting applicable to supply chains. It is also claimed that supply chain attacks are intentional incidents that affect the suppliers.

In CYRENE, we undertake a broader approach, claiming that any incident that causes damage, interruption or delay of the provision of the SCS is considered a threat.

The new [Digital Services Act Package and Digital Markets Act proposals](#) will contribute towards safer SCS. In particular the proposed Digital Services Act introduces a series of rules that, if applicable to SCS, will become resilient to any intentional or unintentional incidents. Among these new rules are:

- removal of illegal goods, services or content online;
- safeguarding users whose content has been erroneously deleted by platforms;
- undertake risk-based action to prevent large scale platforms;
- facilitating access by researchers to key platform data to better understand the operation of the large-scale platforms;
- traceability of business users in online market places, to help track down sellers of illegal goods or services.

The [European Chips Act](#) aims to monitor the industrial supply chains, ensuring the resilience of the entire supply chain including design, production, packaging, equipment and suppliers such as producers of wafers. It will also support the development of European fabrication plants and energy-efficient semiconductors. **If we adopt the CYRENE terminology, the European Chips Act will ensure the technical component perspective of the SCS.**

The proposed [NIS2](#) obliges more entities and sectors to take cybersecurity measures; it addresses, for the first time, cybersecurity of the ICT supply chain (emphasizing the case of IoT) and the streamline reporting obligations. It introduces more stringent supervisory measures and stricter enforcement requirements, including harmonised sanctions across the EU.

CYRENE contributes to the implementation of the NIS2 for the case of the SCS: It proposes the establishment of an online collaborative ISMS for the SCS, hosted and operated by the SCS-Provider where all business partners (e.g.: suppliers, third parties, costumers, consumers) can collaborate and share their cybersecurity intelligence, can perform the SCS-risk assessment, undertake measures and generate the protection profile (PP) of the SCS.

The European Parliament and the Council, Directive, [Cybersecurity Act](#), promotes the cybersecurity certification for ICT products (software, hardware, processes, services) and scales up the response to cyber-attacks, promoting cyber resilience and trust for consumers within the EU. The European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme (EUCC) serves as a template in order to propose security certification schemas for ICT products.

CYRENE proposed a tailored and risk-based security and privacy certification scheme for the SCS based on the EUCC. In particular, CYRENE developed a conformity assessment methodology where an assessor can assess the conformity of the PP of the SCS. The assessor can find all needed information and useful evidence in the SCS-ISMS.

The European Parliament and the Council, Directive, [Liability of defective products](#) includes all defective products. SCS can be considered as a digital product and thus it can fall under this Directive. We can translate defectiveness in the SCS content as an interrupted /damaged and thus no secure SCS.

References

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Supply chain attacks (ENISA 2021), Online Available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/understanding-the-increase-in-supply-chain-security-attacks>

Further Reading

For further reading please read CYRENE Deliverables 2.1, 2.2, 3.1

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